

Food Security and Climate Smart Agriculture in India

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Food security is an alarming issue in present situation where the world is growing rapidly using the available resources, a part of the world population is not even able to afford a sufficient amount of food requirement. However the trend was declining until the covid19 pandemic but after this the trend is found to be rising, total population of the world is increasing and more serious concern is that the changing climatic condition have very high and negative impact on the food production. So aim of this paper is to show how food security and the issue of climate change can be solved by the new approach Climate Smart Agriculture and some of the key government initiatives for CSA.

Key Words: Sustainable Agriculture, Climate Smart Agriculture, Food Security, Undernourishment, Climate Change.

1. Introduction : There is a sudden rise in number of undernourished population in the world this could not have been a tension if this would have vanished with the pandemic, but this pandemic has left people with unemployment, disrupted economic system and market, market prices for food have increased and declining trend in the food production due to changing climate & natural disaster. This study will highlight the severity of Global Food Insecurity and the importance of Climate Smart Agriculture, an approach to transform agriculture-food systems towards green and climate resilient practices along with the major initiatives taken by India for making its agriculture climate resilient, for achieving two Zero Hunger & No Poverty very urgent goal out of Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals, set for the sustainability of mankind. A total number of 828 million peoples were in chronic hunger in 2021 according to Global Hunger Index 2022 (State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World report 2022). The world will need 60% more food to feed the growing estimated population of 9.3 billion by 2050. India itself has 224.3 million hunger populations with 27% global share. On the other hand, the IPCC reports says that in India between 2010 to 2039 the countrywide yields of major crops will be decline as high as 9 % worsening further with time, as up to 20% for wheat, 35% for rice and 60% for maize depending on the future climatic condition and location.

2. Objective: Main objective of the study is to study the need of climate resilient agriculture for achieving the food security and what are the initiatives taken, this objective can be classified as following sub-objective;

- To study the severity, trend and challenges of food security
- To study the impact of climate change and food production
- To make an overview of initiatives taken for Climate Smart Agriculture

3. Research Methodology and Data Source

The study is completely based on secondary data mainly collected from FAO statistics, World Bank data, Public Information Bureau and extensive literature has been reviewed from various journals, Newspapers, Magazines. References are given in the

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bibliography section. The study is analytical in nature so descriptive statistics is used to describe the facts, trends and phenomenon.

4. Food Security Targets and Current Status

4.1 Targets: According to World food Summit 1996, the term food security means “all people at all times, have physical access and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food for meeting the dietary need of any individual for a healthy and active life”, there are four dimensions of food security, physical & economic access, physical availability, food utilization and stability of the previous three dimension. There are Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aiming at the sustainability of the flora and fauna of the world in a more clear way for these all goals for sustainability of mankind indirectly. But SDG1 and SDG2 No poverty and Zero Hunger respectively are direct and immediate aim which will help for this sustainability and Human resource formulation. SDG2 is Zero Hunger which can be achieved by providing food security. By 2030 the target is to end hunger and remove malnutrition of all forms by providing safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year. Another target is to double agricultural productivity and income of small and marginal food producer by other forms of non-farm income. Increase in Investment on agricultural Research and technology. One more target is to prevent trade restrictions on agricultural markets and to ensure proper functioning of food commodity market.

4.2. Current State of Food Insecurity: It is estimated that the prevalence of undernourishment was in a declining trend almost stagnant until 2019 but suddenly rose from 8.0% of global population in 2019 to 9.3% in 2020 and in a slower pace but rose to 9.8% in 2021. From 2019 to 2020, 103 million more people were added to undernourishment, between 2020-21 more 46 million added. We can say since the outbreak of covid19 pandemic 150 million population moved to undernourishment. Out of the 768 million undernourished 425 million is named for Asia. If we talk about the Indian context 53% of Asia’s undernourished population is accounted for India. The following pie chart 1.A, 1.B, 1.C. showing that that prevalence of food insecurity is still very for the current situation and large part of such kind of population is found in Asia more specifically from India.

Year	Prevalence of Undernourishment in Percentage	Number of undernourished in Millions
2005	12.3	805.5
2007	10.5	703.7
2009	9.8	674.5
2011	8.3	586.2
2013	7.9	570.7
2015	8	588.6
2017	7.6	573.3
2019	8	618.4
2021	9.8%	767.9

Figure 1.A. Source: fao.org

Year	Prevalence of Undernourishment in Percentage	Number of undernourished in Millions
2005	21.60	247.80
2007	17.50	207.20
2009	16.30	198.00
2011	15.40	193.10
2013	14.90	190.80
2015	14.50	190.50
2017	13.20	176.30
2019	14.60	200.00
2020	16.50	224.30

Figure 1.B. Source: fao.org

Figure 1.C. Source: fao.org

Figure 2.A. Percentage of World Population that is undernourished is presented in Right hand side Y axis and number of people that is undernourished is presented in left hand side Y axis in Million Source: data.worldbank.org

Figure 2.B.: Percentage of Indian Population that is undernourished is presented in Right hand side Y axis and number of people that is undernourished is presented in left hand side Y axis in Million

Figure 2.A and 2.B respectively present the data of Table no 1.A and Table no. 1.B, where we can find the similar trend in both in India and Global Average prevalence of undernourishment in percentage of total population. Starting from 2005 the trend was declining in both cases until 2019 but afterwards the trend started rising suddenly. One more point to be noted here that world data is shown after a interval of two that is 2019-21 that is the reason why it seems to be more steeper as compare to India which is flatter at the end because at the end of the series data is shown for only one year 2019-20. However we can find slop for both the cases is increasing in terms of percentage and also in number. Rising proportion of undernourished population attributed to prevalent of unemployment, reduction in purchasing power, inefficient market for distribution, inefficient management of food supply chain, increase in food inflation. If we solve these problems we can remove the rising proportion back to declining trend. But after returning declining track how we can fasten the stagnant declining trend is by solving the problem of Low agricultural productivity, food production disrupted by natural disaster and increasing irrigation in rain-fed area, these mentioned factors are directly connected to climate change. Now we have to see the impact of climate change on o know the importance of implementation CSA for Food Security.

5. Impact of climate change and Importance of CSA : Economic and Physical access to food security is dependent upon the efficient market mechanism, food supply chain, purchasing power of the people & its stability and economic growth. However physical availability of food is sufficient in India but above definition includes nutritious food for that diversity in dietary plan is needed for sufficient protein and other nutrition. India is self-sufficient in food production but lagging behind inefficient market mechanism for economic access. But sufficient production of food at current time is also does not ensure food security for this a more than sufficient amount of food production for anytime food availability keeping the future uncertainty in mind also for contribution to global food security. High volume of production is further depending upon the availability of resources such as land, climate, soil quality, water and other infrastructure.

Challenges for physical availability of food production is

- (i) Land Availability

- (ii) Soil Health
- (iii) Water Availability
- (iv) Infrastructural Support
- (v) Climatic Conditions etc.

Climate change is the long term change in weather pattern and shifts in mean temperature, consequences of climate change has direct and indirect negative impact on food production. Food production is directly affected by the changing pattern of rainfall & temperature and increasing number of natural disaster. We can find that tropical regions are more affected by the natural disaster like India for such kind of nature Indian monsoon is known as a gamble monsoon. However natural disaster is not only affecting the tropical rather the whole world is suffering and showing negative impact on agriculture sector. Impact of Climate change on agriculture has been summarized in following points;

- Change in temperature for India is triggered increase from 1901 to 2018 is **0.6°C** to **25.1°C** which is the reason for shift in the monsoon pattern.
- Due to change in rainfall pattern, decrease in groundwater, and rising temperature productivity could fall 10-40% by 2100.
- Another major impact is fall in productivity, between 2010-2039 total losses on yield could be as high as 9% worsening further depending upon the time due to climate change, the loss can be up to 13% for barley, 20% for wheat, 35% for rice and could be as high as 60% for maize.
- United Nation Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNISDR) (2018) from the period of 1998-2017 disaster hit countries has experienced US\$2908 billion economic losses of which 77% loss is accounted to climate change and the trend is increasing.
- An estimated loss of US\$10 billion due to adverse climate is estimated by Government of India's Economic Survey of 2018.

6. Climate Smart Agriculture and Initiatives taken in India

7.1. The Climate Smart Agriculture –Approach : Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) aims to address the interlinked channel of food security and climate change by integrating planning and implementation of sustainable agricultural practices. CSA aims to achieve three wins simultaneously; increased productivity, Enhanced resilience and Reduced Emission. Developing the potential of small holder crop, livestock, fish and forest production. Because agriculture itself produces around one third of the GHGs that is 19-29% also embody a large carbon footprint. The World Bank group is working with countries committed to deliver a CSA; currently 52% of financing in agriculture is targeted climate adaptation and mitigation.

- Climate smart agriculture is the integration of Climate change into planning and development of sustainable agricultural practices.
- CSA is a flexible set of practices to be adopted use of Insurance schemes, Information Technology, value chains, development of innovative practices for emission reduction and strengthening of institutional environment for adoption of CSA.
- Three wins of CSA which has to be simultaneously is gained is
Increased Productivity-
Enhanced Resilience
Reduced emission

6.2. Key Government Initiatives taken for Implementation of CSA National Innovation on Climate Resilient Agriculture (NICRA)

There are sufficient amount of technology available but the use of such techniques is less reason for this is lack of awareness among the stakeholder. Under this project 16,958 program has been conducted with 5,14,816 stakeholder so as to enable wider adoption of such technology. This Project was launched in 2011 with an outlay of 350 crore by Indian Council of Agriculture Research (ICAR) for strategic research on adaptation and mitigation, demonstration of technologies on farmers fields. To make agriculture resilience to climate change by creating awareness among the farmer which scope covers crops, livestock, fisheries and natural resource management.

National Mission on Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA) : National Action Plan for Climate Change was launched in 2008 to address the impact of climate change. Under this 8 sub-mission was introduced with full filling the country's developmental objective, NMSA is one among them which has four components such as Rainfed Area Development Program, On Farm Water Management Program, Soil Health Management Program and Climate Change and Sustainable Agriculture Monitoring, Modeling and Networking Program.

Increasing the productivity, sustainability, remuneration and more resilience in agriculture NMSA was introduced by promoting location specific farming system, soil health management system, soil & moisture conservation technique and efficient water management practices which have been made operational since 2014-15.

Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana- Per Drop More Crop:- A less than half of the land is cultivated for both the kharif and Rabi Season due to lack of irrigation. For increasing the water use efficiency different technology have been promoted for application, storage and distribution system such as drip & sprinkler irrigation system PMKSY have been launched as a national mission with a budget of 53 billion rupees was distributed in 2015-16. Cabinet committee on Economic Affairs decided to allocate an outlay of 50000 crore between the period of 2015-16 to 2019-20. 30.69 lakh ha has been brought under the micro irrigation project and an area of 3.42 lakh ha has been brought under integrated Farming System.

Soil Health Management Scheme: Soil Health Management is a provision for Identifying judicious use of Chemical fertilizer, organic manures and other secondary micronutrients for improving soil health and productivity. 'Soil Health Card' Scheme is introduced in 2015 for providing information to farmer about health of the farmers. Training and demonstrations to balanced use of composition of different nutrients and chemical is also included. Some of the countries have banned some agricultural products of India because of excessive use of chemicals. So the aim of food security is to achieve safe and nutritious food, if we will increase the production by only chemical our target will not be achieve.

Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojna: PMFBY scheme is to insure and ensure farmers income based on their yield. Launched on 2016 and by removing the flaws of earlier agricultural insurance scheme NAIS and MNAIS under One Nation One Scheme, under the scheme different amounts of claims are set for different stages and whole process is covered under the scheme with a less premium burden on farmers. This scheme will be help farmers financially for continuation in their farming, a healthy credit flow to agricultural sector will ensure food security.

National Adaptation Fund For Climate Change: Fund created to meet the cost arising for adaptation of climate change particularly vulnerable to climate change states such as Odisha, West Bengal And Andhra Pradesh. The fund was set up in 2015 and prioritize the need of NAPCC

Climate Smart Village- It aimed to make adaptable people, community and organizations to climate smart Initiatives. Agriculture in India contribute to around 14% of GHG so CSV is also

National Water Mission : The main goal of this mission is minimizing the wastage, conservation and more equitable distribution both across and within state through integrated water resource development and management. It has 5 objective first comprehensive data base in public domain and assessment of the impact of climate change on water resource, Secondly to increase in efficiency of water use by 20%, thirdly Promotion of basin level integrated water resources management. Next is to promote actions of citizen and state for conservation and preservation of water and last on is focused attention to vulnerable areas, Various campaigns run for achieving the objectives are Catch the Rain, Water Talk, Water Tech Talk, Dialogues with DMs, Sahi Fasal.

Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojna- It is an extended scheme under the Soil Health Management of the NMSA. Objectives are to promote commercial certified organic farming, reduced use of pesticide and chemicals.

Biotech-KISAN: To promote innovation and entrepreneurship in agriculture and to empower women farmers. This scheme involves a range of tools using Biotechnology such as Genetically Modified Organism, Use of Bio-pesticides and other technology.

National Livestock Mission : Livestock farming have the potential climate resilience ability this will help the farmer during the season where crops are disrupted by climate or we can say that this scheme will help farmers to make their source of income stable. This is a kind of crop-diversification focuses on entrepreneurship development, breed improvement in poultry, sheep, goat and piggery including their food. Some of the sub-mission of this schemes are Sub-Mission on Breed Development of Livestock & poultry, Feed & Foodder development and sub-mission on Extension and Innovation.

Neem Coated Urea- Is a government scheme supported by the government of India to boost the production of wheat and rice. Under this scheme urea fertilizer is coated by neem seed, for boosting the production of this urea govt. has increased subsidy from 25% to 75%. This will help the farmers to reduce their cost of production, to increase crop specific yields by 15-30%.

7. Conclusion : In the above studies we can find that the prevalence of undernourishment is still very as per the targets set by different organization such as zero hunger & Malnutrition by the end of 2030 and providing food security to the world. It can be found that the rate was declining but at a stagnant rate until 2019 but started increasing which can be removed very soon but to speed up the rate we have take care of the climatic factors which are long term reason for prevailing food insecurity. For this a new approach has been introduced Climate Smart Agriculture which has the potential to tackle the factors who are hurdle for long term. It is a set of integrated planning for adopting sustainable agricultural practices to the interlinked problem of food security and climate change. Various Initiatives has been taken by the government to make the approach successful such as Climate Adaptation Fund, National Mission on Sustainable Agriculture, Need coated Urea, Paramparagat Krishi Vikash Yojna and many more.

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